

Impact of Public Debt on Trade Policy of Pakistan: Time Series Analysis From 1994-2014.

Author's Details:

⁽¹⁾ Abdul Khalid Memon ⁽²⁾ Ghulam Asghar Phulpoto-MS/M.PHIL Scholars ⁽³⁾ Dr. Mohammad Saleh Memon - Assistant Professor –⁽¹⁾⁽²⁾⁽³⁾Department of Business Administration, Shah Abdul Latif University, Khairpur, Sindh, Pakistan

Abstract

Looking at the gaps of trade policy whose major parameters are imports and exports which are to be settled in a way that economy of Pakistan may move forward toward the growth, for the purpose data was collected from ministry of finance government of Pakistan and analysis through SPSS 18 by using linear regression. Researchers concluded that public debt is positively and significantly related with over all imports of Pakistan, and exports of Pakistan.

Introduction

The trade policy is a compilation of rules and set of laws which relate to trade. Trade policy is formulated by public officials. That helps to run the international trade smoothly. Trade policy plays vital role used for the development of nation and through effective trade policy local industries can be protected by imposing heavy burden on importers. Export and import can be the element of trade policy, the trade of goods to overseas country be called an export where as purchasing of foreign contrived goods in the buyers household market is known as import. Export and import enhance the economy of nation and world market become more extensive. Krugman (1994) the key purpose of international trade the cause it is helpful not to imports but sell abroad. So as to Country obtains from trade is the capacity to import things of labor market belongings. Boariu & Bilan, (2007) argue that export development boosts factor output due to the gain obtained from rising profits to size, by catering to the larger foreign market. In adding up, export development relaxes the foreign exchange restraints that result in a boost in the import of assets rigorous intermediary inputs. Due to the increased exports, it needs, if magnitude of imports is approximately equal to that of export, imports clearly have important possible interim efficiency improved for the reason that exporters have a capability to try to win in overseas markets. This result in technical move on and grooming of confined entrepreneurs. The public debt is also called government debt. The part of total debt that is direct accused on government returns is identified as public debt; it is the measurement of government obligations. There are two types of public debt, domestic and external debt, every one of these debts have own earnings and disadvantages. Cunningham R. , (1993) set up that debt weight has insignificant outcome on economic augmentation as the impact on the output of labor and assets.

Makki & Somwaru, (2004) also stated that public debt has each and every one as other loan is expensive as government handover interest to their creditors as a cost for by means of the provisional resource. On the basis of its features, public debt can engage many unwanted effects. The paper established that debt financing guides to the collection of public debt and to the rise in interest payable that shows the sign of enhance in budgetary operating cost have to cover. The paper on the other hand constituted that public debt does show the way to the unfair increase of the sum of financial symbols which are in flow and it does not usually have an inflationary aspect. As a result, it is typically approved as a basis to finance budget shortfall in modern society. Public debt has significant impact on economy together in the long term and short term. Public debt has also negative crash on capital accumulation same as productivity and reduce economic expansion.

Literature Review

Chaudhary & Qaisrani, (2002) have investigated important role of trade instability on investment and economic growth. The results of sell to the other countries instability doesn't show directly affect the investment and the economic progress in Pakistan.

Bader, (2006) provides empirical evidence in support of hypothesis that capital goods and imports of intermediate are critical inputs in the export production of Pakistan.

Alfaro, Chanda, Ozcan, & Sayek, (2004) The Pakistan's trade sector is creating valuable relationship in the most of the world's countries which are close to Pakistan. There is huge quantity of goods and products are exported and imported to meet the consumers' satisfaction from different countries.

Balassa, (1978) Explained that exports enhanced the economic growth of the country, where as he pursued promotion of exports policies and achieved substantial development of economy. Furthermore he described increase export growth and increase economic growth, the rate of exchange occurs different time periods.

Amsden, (1989) Stated that appearance of new “Asian Tiger” is durable due to effective interest, subsidies, management investment, and controlled industry by using political as well as threatening sticks.

Arize, (1996, 1998) Mentioned that the irrelevant short run and long run connection between exchange rate volatility on exports and imports.

Edwards, (1987) extreme real exchange rate inconsistency has pessimistic welfare effect, it reduces the rank of international trade, and influence hampers economic growth and investment decisions.

Grossman & Helpman, (1991) beside others, has mentioned to another vital mechanism through trade can improve growth. In the world where firm productivity is independent both on the variety and on quantity of intermediates, admittance to imports can progress productivity through the rising the assortment of intermediates. It may be significant in sectors like electronics where there huge number of expert inputs.

Broll & Eckwert, (1999) the options to exports in the world market boost by exchange rate volatility. Higher volatility raises the prospective gains from international trade, which builds production more beneficial. An additional volatile exchange rate entails higher risk disclosures for international firms and consequence works in the contrary direction and tendencies to reduce production and quantity of international trade. The net outcome of exchange rate volatility on exports and production depends on the level of risk aversion of the firm.

Ali & Chani, (2013) examine the disaggregated import demand purpose for Pakistan. They finish off that the imports of Pakistan are extremely aware to prices and income in Pakistan.

Cunningham, (1993) originate that debt load has a negative economic growth the reason is that the force on the productivity of capital and labor.

Cohen, (1993) Found that the stage of debt doesn't clarify the hold back of investment in extremely indebted developing countries.

Warner, (1992) advises that the causes behind the turn down of investment in several of the profoundly indebted countries are moribund exports prices, elevated world interest rates, and slothful growth. These surprises could have straight caused investment to turn down.

Deshpande, (1997) also come up to finale that the link between investment and external debt is negative.

In one more study, Waheed, (2006) accomplished that domestic debt fill the primary deficit. During the Fiscal alteration reduce the primary deficit. This modification must not be attained on the charge of engrave in progress expenditure somewhat there is require for grave efforts to raise domestic tax income.

Keynes, (1929) external borrowings boost a country's admittance to resources even as domestic borrowing barely transfers resources inside the country. In further terms domestic borrowing merely adjusts offers of money holders whereas money ruins same. So, just external debt produces a “transfer” problem.

Islam, (1992) observes this matter for the case of Bangladesh with time series statistics cover the period 1972–1988. His result advice a feeble positive relation of debt on growth, even as in common domestic resources show to apply stronger force than foreign resources.

Diamond, (1965) the most well-known apprehension as regards domestic debt is the multitude cause on the private investment. While governments borrow nationally, they employ up domestic private reserves that would or else have been accessible for private subdivision lending. In turn, the minor residual lake of loan able finances in the market increases the expenditure of capital for the private borrowers, falling private investments require, and thus capital development, increase and welfare.

Buchanan, (1958) and Meade, (1958) disputed that the public debt is a load for next generation, which come up to in the shape of a abridged flow of returns from a inferior stock of private investments. Separately from a directly crowding-out root, it besides meaningful away to the shock on long-standing interest rates, perhaps in non-linear shape if the government process is of substantial size it may considerably drive up long-term interest rates while the fall of private capital will lean to boost its insignificant product . Smooth when the public debt is produced while a counter-cyclical compute the easiest probable monetary policy through the entire arrangement of interest rate abridged to its lowly feasible level, the debt raise will in general not be costless for upcoming generations in spite of being beneficial to the present generation.

Research Model

Hypothesis

- H1: Exports are negatively related with public debt.
- H2: Imports are positively related with public debt.
- H3: Exports and Imports are highly correlated with each other.

Data (1994-2014)

Amount Rs in Billions.

Year	Exports	Imports	Domestic Debt	External Debt	Total Public Debt
1994	251.173	320.892	767.9	881	1,648.9
1995	294.741	397.575	790	873	1,662
1996	325.313	465.001	901.4	975.9	1,877.3
1997	373.160	436.338	1037.2	1147.3	2,184.5
1998	390.342	465.964	1,176	1,496	2,672
1999	443.67	533.792	1,376	1,759	3,135
2000	539.070	627.000	1,560	1,856	3,416
2001	560.947	634.630	1,731.0	2,060.8	3,791.8
2002	652.294	714.372	1,717.9	2,005.6	3,723.7
2003	709.036	897.825	1,853.7	1,927.7	3,781.4
2004	854.088	1,223.079	1,979.5	1,937.5	3,917
2005	984.841	1,711.158	2,178	1,913	4,091
2006	1,029.312	1,851.806	2337	1973	4310
2007	1,196.638	2,512.072	2,601	2,201	4,802
2008	1,383.718	2,723.570	3,266	2,778	6,044
2009	1,617.458	2,910.975	3,852	3,776	7,629
2010	2,120.847	3,455.287	4,651	4,270	8,921
2011	2,120.847	3,455.286	6,014	4,694	10,709
2012	2,110.605	4,009.093	6,223	4,773	10,996
2013	1,343.192	2,456.663	8,786	4,831	12,727
2014	1,542.501	2,707.852	10,823	4,711	15,534

Sources: i) SBP ii) MoF

Methodology

Data Collection Method:

Secondary data collection method was used for the collection of data regarding over all imports, exports and public debt, from ministry of finance government of Pakistan and entered in the SPSS 18 for applying linear regression to check the inter relationship between the variables mentioned above to predict the imports and exports.

Results and Discussions:

Diagnosis Test 1

$$\text{Imports} = \alpha + PD\beta + \mu$$

Table 1

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.813 ^a	.661	.643	706.01970

a. Predictors: (Constant), Debt

Table 2

ANOVA^b

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	1.752E7	1	1.752E7	35.156	.000 ^a
	Residual	8972348.778	18	498463.821		
	Total	2.650E7	19			

a. Predictors: (Constant), Debt

b. Dependent Variable: Imports

According to the results are adjusted are requires which shares over all fitness of the model that is 0.643 and model is significant at 0.000 level, which clearly states that public debt is the major contributor to predict the imports.

Table 3

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	244.157	271.352		.900	.380
	Debt	.241	.041	.813	5.929	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Imports

Public debt is positively and significantly relative with inputs, strength of relationship of public debt is too much high with the imports.

Diagnosis Test 2

$$\text{Exports} = \alpha + \text{PD}\beta + \mu$$

Table 4

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.838 ^a	.702	.686	333.91830

a. Predictors: (Constant), Debt

Table 5

ANOVA^b

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	4735768.410	1	4735768.410	42.473	.000 ^a
	Residual	2007025.802	18	111501.433		
	Total	6742794.212	19			

a. Predictors: (Constant), Debt

b. Dependent Variable: Exports

According to the table 4 over all fitness of the model is 0.686 that is also significant at 0.000 level, which states that public debt is not only a predictor of imports but the exports as well.

Table 6

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	240.875	128.339		1.877	.077
	Debt	.125	.019	.838	6.517	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Exports

Value of Beta for public debt is 0.838 that is positively and significantly related with exports.

Conclusions

Budget deficit is the problem of many economic systems which can be improved through different policies. Analysis in this regard research was carried out, and results suggested that public debt is directly related with inputs which can be controlled by encouraging exports favored policies which is logically proved in this study that public debt is directly and significantly related with the exports.

Limitations

Study was limited:

1. Time horizon
2. Economic conditions of Pakistan
3. Exchange rate fluctuation

Bibliography

- Alfaro, L., Chanda, A., Ozcan, S., & Sayek, S. (2004). FDI and Economic Growth: The Role of Local Financial Markets. *Journal of International Economic* , 64, 113-134.
- Ali, A., & Chani, I. M. (2013). Disaggregate Import Demand Function: A Case Study of Pakistan. *International Journal of Economics and Empirical Research* , 1 (1), 1-14.
- Amsden, L. (1989). *Asia's Next Giant: South Korea and Late Industrialisation*. New York: Oxford University Press .
- Arize, A. C. (1996, 1998). The Effect of Exchange Rate Uncertainty on Export Growth Evidence from Korean Data. *International Economic Journal* , 10 (3), 49-60.
- Balassa, B. (1978). exports and Economic Growth; Further Evidence. *Journal of Economic Development* , 05, 181-189.
- Boariu, A., & Bilan, I. (2007). Inflationary Effects if Budget Deficit Financing in Contemporary Economies.
- Broll, U., & Eckwert, B. (1999). Exchange Rate Volatility and International Trade. *Southern Economic Journal* , 66:1, 178-185.
- Buchanan, J. M. (1958). *Public Principles of the Public Debt*, Homewood, Illinois.
- Chaudhary, & Qaisrani. (2002). Trade Instability, Investment and Economic Growth in Pakistan. *Pakistan Economic and Social Review* , XL, NO. 1 (Summer), pp 57-73.
- Cohen, D. (1993). Low Investment and Large LCD Debt in the 1980.s. *The American Economic Review* , 83:3, 437-449.
- Cohen, D. (1993). Low Investment and Large LCD Debt in the 1980.s. *The American Economic Review* , 83:3, 437-449.
- Cunningham, R. T. (1993). The Effect of Debt Burden on Economic Growth in Heavily Indebted Nations. *Journal of Economic Development* , 115-126.
- Cunningham, R. (1993). "The Effects of Debt Burden on Economic Growth in Heavily Indebted Nations". *Journal of Economic Development* , pp, 115-126.
- Deshpande, A. (1997). The Debt Overhang and the Disincentive to Invest. *Journal of Development Economics* , 169-187.
- Diamond, P. (1965). "National Debt in a Newclassical Debt Model,". *Journal of Political Economy* , Vol. 55, 1126-1150.

Edwards, S. (1987). Real Exchange Rate Variability: An Empirical Analysis of the Developing Countries Case. *International Economic Journal* , 1:1, 91-106.

Grossman, G., & Helpman, E. (1991). *Innovation and Growth in Global Economy*. Cambridge, The MIT Press .

Islam, A. (1992). "Foreign aid and Economic Growth: An Econometric Study for Bangladesh". *Applied Economic Letters* , 24:, 541-544.

Makki, & Somwaru. (2004). *Comparative Analysis of the Impacts on Economic Growth of Selected Countries in Central Asia; A Qualitative Approach*.

Meade, J. E. (1958). "Is the National Debt a Burden?". *Oxford Economic Papers, New Series* , Vol. 10 (2), pp. 163-183.

Waheed, A. (2006). *Sustainability and Determinants of Domestic Public Debt of Pakistan*. Nagoya University Japan. (CSID Discussion Paper No: 137) .

Warner, A. M. (1992). Did the Debt Crisis Cause the Investment Crisis. *Quarterly Journal of Economics* , 1161-1186.